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NEWSLETTER #4

ELASTIC enters its next phase with strong momentum

The ELASTIC project has successfully completed its mid-term reporting period, with strong progress across research, technical development, demonstrator preparation, dissemination, standardisation, and exploitation activities. During RP1, the consortium advanced its work on secure and portable orchestration for 6G edge-cloud services, including WebAssembly, eBPF, confidential computing, and distributed service management.

Following this milestone, ELASTIC has released the **RP1 Results Presentation and Research Outputs**, providing a consolidated overview of the main outcomes achieved during the first reporting period. This includes progress across work packages, technological developments, demonstrator preparation, research outputs, and activities related to dissemination, exploitation, and standardisation.

[Read more](#)

News & Highlights

From Chania review preparation to RP1 results

The consortium meeting in Chania, held on 22–23 September 2025 and hosted by the Technical University of Crete, focused on review preparation and alignment across partners. This meeting supported the consolidation of progress that was later reflected in the RP1 results and mid-term reporting.

[Read more](#)

Consortium meeting in Lund: moving towards integration and validation

In January 2026, ELASTIC partners met in Lund to accelerate integration across the project's secure orchestration stack. Discussions focused on demonstrator maturity, remote attestation, confidential workload execution, edge AI integration, and policy-driven security orchestration. With core components becoming technically solid, the project is now moving into a decisive phase of system-level consolidation and validation.

[Read more](#)

Press release: ELASTIC mid-term success

The ELASTIC mid-term press release summarises the project's progress during RP1, including architectural work, first prototype versions, demonstrator definition, ecosystem engagement, scientific publications, dissemination activities, exploitation planning, and standardisation contributions.

[Read more](#)

Events & Webinars

ELASTIC Participates in the Women in ICT Standardisation Webinar – 5th Edition

ELASTIC supported this initiative as part of its broader engagement with the research and innovation community and ongoing visibility efforts around inclusion in ICT standardisation.

[Read more](#)

ELASTIC & 6G-PATH Webinar: Intelligent Orchestration Across the Edge-Cloud Continuum

This joint webinar highlighted intelligent orchestration approaches across distributed environments and showcased synergies between ELASTIC and 6G-PATH.

[Read more](#)

Demo Series: showing ELASTIC technologies in practice

The ELASTIC Demo Series presents key project technologies and demonstrator progress in a clear and accessible format.

Demonstrator 1: Smart Connected Factory of the Future

Demonstrator 1 focuses on real-time, secure, and scalable data processing across edge, fog, and cloud in a manufacturing setting. It combines technologies such as WebAssembly, Trusted Execution Environments, federated learning, and dynamic orchestration to support predictive maintenance, cross-factory data sharing, and low-latency robot control.

[Read more](#)

Demonstrator 2 MVP: Migration of a Sensitive IT Service to the Public Cloud

Demonstrator 2 MVP presents ELASTIC's approach to privacy-preserving cloud migration for sensitive IT services. Using the Badge Request Tool use case, the demo shows trusted execution with verified trust checks and the basis for continuous security monitoring.

[Read more](#)

Propeller: lightweight orchestration beyond Kubernetes

The Propeller demo presents a WebAssembly-based orchestrator that supports running application logic from cloud systems down to small edge and IoT devices.

[Read more](#)

Wasm-operator: efficient Kubernetes orchestration with WebAssembly

The Wasm-operator demo explores how WebAssembly can support more efficient Kubernetes orchestration. It addresses the role of operators in automating lifecycle management of cloud-native applications, while reducing overhead through Wasm-based execution.

[Read more](#)

Scientific contribution

Lost in the Pages: WebAssembly Code Recovery through SEV-SNP's Exposed Address Space

Authors: Markus Berthlsson, Christian Gehrman
Conference: 31st Australasian Conference on Information Security and Privacy (ACISP 2026)

This publication examines security risks in WebAssembly execution within AMD SEV-SNP confidential computing environments, focusing on code recovery through exposed address-space information.

[Read more](#)

Non-Clashing Teaching in Graphs: Algorithms, Complexity, and Bounds

Authors: Sujoy Bhore, Liana Khazaliya, Fionn Mc Inerney
Conference: The Fourteenth International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2026)

This publication investigates algorithmic and complexity aspects of non-clashing teaching in graph structures, introducing improved algorithmic results, stronger lower bounds, and combinatorial upper bounds for broader graph classes.

[Read more](#)

Makespan Minimization in Split Learning: From Theory to Practice

Authors: Robert Ganian, Fionn Mc Inerney, Dimitra Tsigkari
Conference: 2026 IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM 2026)

This publication explores scheduling and optimisation challenges in split learning systems, bridging theoretical models and practical implementation aspects to improve efficiency in distributed machine learning environments.

[Read more](#)

Resilient Automatic Model Selection for Mobility Prediction

Authors: Syafiq Al Atiq, Christian Gehrman, Karim Khalil, Jakob Sternby, Yachao Yuan
Journal: Cluster Computing, 2025

This publication presents a resilient automatic model-selection approach for mobility prediction, aiming to improve reliability and adaptability in dynamic and distributed computing environments.

[Read more](#)

On Using Secure Aggregation in Differentially Private Federated Learning with Multiple Local Steps

Author: Mikko A. Heikkilä
Journal: Transactions on Machine Learning Research (TMLR)

This publication investigates the use of secure aggregation in differentially private federated learning, focusing on privacy protection and efficiency when multiple local training steps are performed.

[Read more](#)

ELASTIC at EuCNC & 6G Summit 2026

ELASTIC will participate in the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2026, taking place from 2–5 June 2026 in Málaga, Spain. Visitors will be able to meet the project team at **Booth 76** and learn more about ELASTIC's work on secure and efficient orchestration across the cloud-edge continuum.

The project will showcase technologies and approaches related to WebAssembly, lightweight orchestration, confidential computing, and distributed service management for next-generation 6G infrastructures.

We look forward to connecting with researchers, industry representatives, and the broader SNS community!

As ELASTIC enters the next phase, the focus is moving from foundations and early results toward integration, demonstrator validation, standardisation, and exploitation. Follow our website and social media channels for upcoming updates, demo releases, publications, and project events.

Stay updated with the latest ELASTIC news, research outputs, demonstrator progress, events, and publications.

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